

COMPARATIVE LINGUISTICS IN THE STUDY OF UZBEK AND ENGLISH

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Abstract. *This article expresses information on comparative linguistics in the study of Uzbek and English.*

Keywords: *Segmental features, syllables, words, phrases and relative level of emphasis and tone in speech, Segmental phonemes.*

СОПОСТАВИТЕЛЬНОЕ ЯЗЫКОПОЛОЖЕНИЕ В ИЗУЧЕНИИ УЗБЕКСКОГО И АНГЛИЙСКОГО ЯЗЫКОВ

Аннотация. *В данной статье изложены сведения сравнительного языкознания при изучении узбекского и английского языков.*

Ключевые слова: *сегментарные признаки, слоги, слова, словосочетания и относительный уровень ударения и тона в речи, сегментарные фонемы.*

In order for representatives of all nationalities living in Uzbekistan to interact equally with representatives of local nationalities in the process of studying and working, to freely exchange ideas in all areas, it will be necessary to meet the requirements of the international standard of language education, to form their competence to be able to freely communicate in accordance with various speech situations. In this regard, the decision of the first president of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated December 10, 2012 No. 1875 “on measures to further improve the system of foreign languages \ u200b \ u200bAnd reforms carried out on teaching foreign languages \ u200b \ u200bThe specially adopted decision of the world's leading countries and the implementation of the competency approach, the development of a system of training and retraining of teachers of a foreign language, the provision of the educational process with educational and methodological literature and modern tools has become extremely important in the field of Education. It should be noted that this decision caused great work in our country to further improve not only foreign languages, but also language education, including the teaching of the Uzbek language, which is the state language of the Republic, to coordinate the requirements of the DTS in the subject of the Uzbek language with the requirements of international standards and to introduce.

In the study of any foreign language, although ignored, the issues of phonetics and Phonology are important. The ability to speak and understand a foreign language depends on the skills acquired in phonetics.

The Departments of phonetics and orthoepy are one of the initial and most difficult stages of learning any language. As one of the neglected aspects of English language teaching, pronunciation came into consideration again in the last half of the 20th century with the development of audio and direct style. Over the past period, teachers and applied linguists have recognized the difficulty of teaching correct pronunciation skills, and much research has been devoted to this issue. In this regard, they tried to develop different methods and techniques, relying on other disciplines such as phonetics, phonology, and mastering a second language among others. Taking phonetics and Phonology as molds, teachers tried to use the various components of these

basic subjects to apply them in the course process. In this way, it is manifested that the importance of phonetics and Phonology is important in teaching correct pronunciation. Different components of the study of phonetics and Phonology are distinguished by their connection with the teaching of pronunciation.

Pennington and Richards (1986) divided pronunciation into four main components:

- segmental properties: minimum sound units defined phonetically;
- sound tuning features: General articular features of speech;
- prosodic features: the relative level of emphasis and tone in syllables, words, phrases and speech.

The development of audio required special attention to "listening and repetition". This approach is aimed at the formation of the skill of listening and repeated pronunciation, in which the teacher told students that he should repeat individual words, and the more repetitions (imitation) are formed, the more pronounced the pronunciation of students. Later, due to the fact that with the development of the communicative movement in the 1970s and 1980s, the traditional method was used in the passage of classes in this direction, for some time remained out of sight. However, with the rapid growth of linguistic research and the study of phonology in the late 1980s, the rules of orthoepy drew the attention of teachers and applied linguists to itself. They mainly tried to create techniques and methods to harmonize the teaching of correct pronunciation with other basic language skills.

In this regard, the author develops a hierarchy of priorities that are used in teaching pronunciation. Priority is given to training from the highest to the lowest level:

1. Suprasegmental phonemes.
2. Segmental phonemes.
3. Allophones in additional distribution.
4. All sounds in free exchange.

One of the well-known methods used in teaching pronunciation is phonemes and allows you to use a minimum of pairs. Cook (2008) notes that the concepts of phoneme and minimum pair were useful in preparing materials for teaching pronunciation. Usually students are accompanied by words such as " machine " / ka: / or " cow " / kaʊ / or " bra " / bra / and " eyebrow " / braʊ/. Then, they are asked whether they make a difference or not. This allows the teacher to structure the entire phonemic inventory from scratch. In addition, learning to distinguish one phoneme from another for students is facilitated by isolating the minimum pair.

the time spent teaching pronunciation will depend on the priorities of the general course. More precisely, the practice of pronunciation can be included in the lesson in any place where you notice an important problem. Broughton and others. al (ibid) further provides some guidelines that can be applied to teaching pronunciation, the main ones being the following:

- The practice of recognition must precede the practice of production.
- The sound that must be heard and said must be clearly highlighted in short sentences.
- Students should be given the opportunity to hear what is said in several voices as a model.
- Sounds in English can be represented differently from other English sounds or differently from sounds in the native language.

Making sure you use variety in your pronunciation lessons, your students will make your English pronunciation more successful and gain confidence in it.

Generally speaking, pronunciation teaching has been developing rapidly since the emergence of the traditional approach to Language Teaching. However, with increased attention to the student in the student-oriented approach and constant attention to the communicative side of language teaching, teachers are looking for new ways to add pronunciation to other language skills. As a result, pronunciation was mainly associated with speech and listening. Nevertheless, one should not deny the role of phonetics and Phonology in teaching pronunciation, since the more students know the laws and foundations of these areas of education, the more aware they are of the fine rules of the language.

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